

The Prevalence and Antibiotic Resistance of Pathogenic Bacteria in Respiratory Tract Samples in Basra City, Iraq

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Abstract

Background: Respiratory tract infections (RTIs) are a serious health problem worldwide. They cause a variety of health problems and can even be deadly, particularly such as the elderly and children. **Objective:** Investigate the prevalence and antibiotic-resistant bacteria in patients with respiratory tract infections (RTIs). **Methodology:** A sample of 274 clinical specimens (sputum, swabs, pleural fluids, and bronchial washings) was taken in patients with respiratory tract infections in the period between February and October 2024 in the Al-Sader teaching hospital in Basrah. The VITEK 2 Compact system was used to identify bacteria and determine antimicrobial susceptibility through the use of the established microbiological protocols and the CLSI (2024) guidelines. IBM SPSS (v.25) was used to analyze the data statistically; the level of statistical significance was $p < 0.05$. **Results:** Out of 274 samples, the highest culture positivity was recorded for sputum samples (63.43%), while throat swabs had the lowest (22.22%). *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was the most common among all isolates, indicating its importance in respiratory infections when compared to other bacteria identified. Gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *K. pneumoniae*), showed high resistance against most tested antibiotics. However, some antibiotics, such as amikacin, meropenem, and colistin, remain effective against most of the tested isolates. Also, gram-positive bacteria (*Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Staphylococcus aureus*) showed high resistance, especially against macrolides and fluoroquinolones. **Conclusion:** *K. pneumoniae*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus* are the most common respiratory infections. The sustained efficacy of last-line agents such as carbapenems, colistin, vancomycin, and linezolid is vital.

Introduction

Respiratory tract infections (RTIs) are a serious health problem worldwide. They cause a variety of health problems and can even be deadly, particularly in susceptible populations such as the elderly, children, and those with weakened immune systems [1]. Respiratory tract infections refer to any infection that affects the upper or lower respiratory system [2]. Infections of the upper respiratory tract (URTIs) can include tonsillitis, the common cold, rhinitis, pharyngitis, otitis media, and laryngitis [3]. Infections of the lower respiratory tract (LRTIs) involve acute pneumonia and bronchitis [4]. Several bacteria,

causative agents of respiratory tract infections, such as *Klebsiella pneumoniae* [5], *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Hemophilus influenzae*, *Moraxella catarrhalis* [6], and *Staphylococcus aureus* [7].

Antibiotic-resistant bacteria pose a significant public health risk, threatening the successful treatment of various bacterial diseases. It occurs when bacteria develop their ability to survive when exposed to antibiotics, which would typically kill or restrict their development [8]. The development of these problems leads to more challenges in infection treatment, longer sickness, more expensive medical care, and even

More Information

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mortality [9]. Antibacterial resistance have different mechanisms, for instance, enzymatic inactivation of antibacterials, target site modifications, increased efflux pumps, decreased influx, and biofilm formation [10]. Understanding pathogenic bacteria prevalence and patterns of antibiotic resistance in respiratory tract samples is critical to creating successful treatment techniques and using targeted infection control measures. However, there is not enough detailed local data from Basrah city, Iraq, emphasizing the necessity for updated research. Therefore, the aim of the current study was to determine the prevalence and distribution of pathogenic bacteria that cause respiratory tract infections. As well as determine the susceptibility patterns to commonly used antibiotics among patients at Al-Sader Teaching Hospital in Basrah City, Iraq.

Materials and Methods

Clinical Samples Collection

A total of 274 clinical samples were collected from patients with RTIs, during the period from February to October 2024 at Al-Sader Teaching Hospital in Basrah, Iraq. The clinical samples included sputum (134), throat swabs (27), nasal swabs (15), pleural fluids (74), and bronchial washings (24).

Bacterial Identification and Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing

The samples (274) were sent to the microbiology laboratory and followed standard microbiological procedures. Samples were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours on appropriate bacteriological culture media (blood agar, MacConkey agar, eosin methylene blue, mannitol salt agar, and chocolate agar). Used VITEK® 2 Compact system (bioMérieux, France) to identify the bacterial isolates and to test them for antibiotic susceptibility in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions. Seventeen antibiotics were chosen for the antibiotic sensitivity of gram-negative bacteria, including Piperacillin/Tazobactam, Ampicillin, Ampicillin/Sulbactam, Cefoxitin, Cefotaxime, Ceftazidime, Ceftriaxone, Cefepime, Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole, Aztreonam, Meropenem, Imipenem, Amikacin, Gentamicin, Ciprofloxacin, Levofloxacin, and Colistin. Fourteen antibiotics were tested for gram-positive bacteria, including Cefoxitin, Oxacillin, Gentamicin, Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole, Vancomycin, Erythromycin, Azithromycin, Linezolid, Doxycycline, Tetracycline, Clindamycin, Rifampicin, Levofloxacin, and Ciprofloxacin. The antimicrobial susceptibility results was assessed based on the clinical and laboratory standards institute guidelines [11].

Statistical Analysis

IBM SPSS Statistics (version 25) was used in the statistical analysis. The percentages and frequencies were calculated with descriptive statistics. Chi-square (χ^2) test used to determine the correlations between bacterial results and patient characteristics (e.g., age group, sex, and sample type). Statistical significance was determined when the *p-value* was less than 0.05.

Results and Discussion

A total of 274 clinical samples (including 134 sputum, 27 throat swabs, 15 nasal swabs, 74 pleural fluids, and 24 bronchial washings) were obtained from patients with respiratory tract infections. The result (Table 1) showed, out of the 274 samples, 114 samples (41.61%) were negative for bacterial growth, whereas 160 samples (58.39%) were positive. Out of the 134 samples that were collected from sputum, 85 (63.43%) were culture-positive. *K. pneumoniae* (32.94%), *P. aeruginosa* (22.35%), and *S. aureus* (11.76%) are the most common bacteria found in sputum samples. While, out of the 74 pleural fluid samples, 46 (62.16%) had positive cultures. *K. pneumoniae* remained the most common (30.43%), with *S. pneumoniae* and *S. aureus* (21.74% each). Out of the 27 throat swabs, 6 (22.22%) had positive cultures of *S. pyogenes* (50%), *K. pneumoniae* (33.33%), and *H. influenza* (16.67%). Out of 24 bronchial wash samples showed 15 (62.5%) showed positive cultures, including four bacteria. *P. aeruginosa* (33.33%), *K. pneumoniae* (26.67%), and both *A. baumannii* and *Citrobacter freundii* (20%). From the 15 nasal swab samples, 8 (53.33%) were included, *S. aureus* (75%) and *S. epidermidis* (25%).

This study showed a clear difference in bacterial isolates based on the type of respiratory samples. *K. pneumoniae* was identified as the most common pathogen, particularly among lower respiratory tract samples like sputum and pleural fluid. The result aligns with several local studies that confirmed *K. pneumoniae* causes a serious of respiratory tract infections in Iraq, such as in Basrah [12], Baghdad [13], and Al-Ramadi [14].

The distribution and prevalence of *P. aeruginosa* in bronchial wash and sputum indicate its proven importance in nosocomial infections. In addition to adapting to wet conditions, notably ventilator-associated pneumonia settings [15]. *S. aureus* has a high prevalence in nasal, sputum, and pleural samples, which is consistent with how it acts as both a commensal and opportunistic pathogen in the respiratory system [16].

Table 1: The Distribution of Bacteria Isolated from Different Sites of the Respiratory Tract

No.	Samples	Number of samples	Growth		Bacteria	Number of species	Percentage (%)
			+	-			
1	Sputum	134	85	49	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	28	32.94

					<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	19	22.35
					<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	10	11.76
					<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	8	9.41
					<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	7	8.24
					<i>Escherichia coli</i>	7	8.24
					<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>	2	2.35
					<i>Haemophilus influenzae</i>	2	2.35
					<i>Moraxella catarrhalis</i>	1	1.18
					<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>	1	1.18
2	Throat Swab	27	6	21	<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	3	50
					<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	2	33.33
					<i>Haemophilus influenzae</i>	1	16.67
3	Nasal swab	15	8	7	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	6	75
					<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	2	25
4	Pleural fluid	74	46	28	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	14	30.43
					<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	10	21.74
					<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	10	21.74
					<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	4	8.7
					<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	3	6.52
					<i>Escherichia coli</i>	3	6.52
					<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	2	4.35
5	bronchial wash	24	15	9	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	5	33.33
					<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	4	26.67
					<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>	3	20
					<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	3	20
Total		274	160	114			

Pearson Chi-Square= 201.779, df= 48, p-value= 0.001
 The result of the distribution of 160 bacterial species (Figure 1) in five age groups (10–24, 25–39, 40–54, 55–69, and 70 years and above). Showed that the most commonly isolated bacterium was *K. pneumoniae*, with the highest numbers, which accounted for 30.0% (48 isolates) of all cases, followed by *P. aeruginosa* 17.5% (28 isolates) and *S. aureus* 16.3% (26 isolates). *S. pneumoniae* represented 10.6% (17 isolates), while *A. baumannii* recorded 8.8% (14 isolates). Lower detection rates were recorded for *E. coli* 6.3% (10 isolates), *C. freundii* 2.5% (4 isolates), *H. influenzae* 1.9% (3 isolates), *S. pyogenes* 1.9% (3 isolates), *B. fragilis* 1.3% (2 isolates), *E. cloacae* and *S. epidermidis* both 1.3% (2 isolates for each). *M. catarrhalis* was the least frequent, recorded only 0.6% (1 isolate) of the total. Across all age groups, the highest bacterial recovery was observed among individuals aged 55–69 years, followed by those aged (40–54) years. *K. pneumoniae* and *P. aeruginosa* remained the highest isolates in nearly every age group, whereas *M. catarrhalis* appeared solely in the (10–24) years category. Although there was no statistically significant, show that respiratory infections were evenly distributed among age groups in our sample collection, with no clear pattern.

This result contradicts several studies that demonstrate higher rates of *K. pneumoniae* and *A. baumannii* in older individuals due to age-related immunological weakening and higher rates of hospitalization [17,18]. Despite no finding of significance, descriptive patterns show that *K. pneumoniae* and *P. aeruginosa* were more frequently identified in older age groups (≥55 years), possibly due to comorbidities and prolonged hospital stays, both established risk factors in nosocomial infections [19,20]. On the other hand, Pathogens such as *S. aureus* and *S. pneumoniae*, were more uniformly dispersed, indicating that they are prevalent respiratory flora having pathogenic potential in all age groups [21,22].
 Among the 160 culture-positive respiratory samples, including 95 (59.4%) males and 65 (40.6%) females, the result showed no statistically significant association between sex and the distribution of bacterial species (Figure 2). *K. pneumoniae* was the most commonly isolated bacterium in sex groups, with 30.0% (48 isolates) of the total, with a slightly higher occurrence in males (18.8%) than in females (11.3%). The second most prevalent bacteria was *P. aeruginosa* (17.5%; 28 isolates), which was similarly more common in men (10.62% men compared to 6.87% females). Closely followed (16.25%; 26) were *S. aureus* isolates (5.62%

men compared to 3.12% females). Other pathogens, such as *S. pneumoniae*, *E. coli*, and *A. baumannii*, were

also identified as being more common in males than females.

Figure 1: Distribution of Culture-Positive Respiratory Bacteria Cases According to Age Groups

Note: Pearson Chi-Square= 25.659, df= 48, p-value = 0.997

The distribution of respiratory pathogens demonstrated no statistically significant gender-based variations, indicating that the type of infecting bacteria in respiratory tract infections in this population is not influenced by sex. Some previous studies reported different bacterial patterns across sex in respiratory diseases. When it involves respiratory tract infections (RTIs), men are often more vulnerable than women, showing increased susceptibility, more severe infection

progression, and higher mortality rates [23,24]. Despite no finding of statistical significance, descriptive statistics indicate that male individuals had somewhat higher infection frequencies for nearly all important pathogenic bacteria. This pattern may be attributable to behavioral and workplace exposures, higher smoking prevalence, or changes in health-seeking behavior, which are known to alter respiratory health and infection risk [25,26].

Figure 2: Sex-Wise Distribution of Patients with Respiratory Infection

Note: Pearson Chi-Square= 1.843, df= 12, P-value= 1.000

Antibiotic resistance profiles were analyzed for 100 isolate of gram-negative bacteria and 24 isolate of gram-positive bacteria. Gram-negative bacteria included, *P. aeruginosa* (n=28), *E. coli* (n=10), *A.*

baumannii (n=14), and *K. pneumoniae* (n=48). Gram positive bacteria included *S. aureus* (n=15) and *S. pneumoniae* (n=9). In gram-negative bacteria, the result (Table 2) of showed high levels of antibiotic

resistance have been reported by *E. coli*, which resistant to ampicillin (100%), ceftriaxone (92%), cefotaxime (90%), and ceftazidime (85%). however, was minimal resistance to amikacin (5%), and to carbapenems (meropenem 10%, imipenem 12%). In addition, *P. aeruginosa* recorded high resistance to ciprofloxacin 75%, ceftazidime 70%, and cefepime (60%). carbapenem resistance was moderate for imipenem (45%) and for meropenem (40%). In contrast to colistin resistance, which recorded lower resistance at 4%. *A. baumannii* showed very high resistance across most antibiotics, with resistance exceeding ciprofloxacin (92%), both levofloxacin and ceftazidime (90%). While it reached cefepime (88%), both

ampicillin/sulbactam and gentamicin (85%). The other antibiotics recorded piperacillin/tazobactam (80%), for meropenem (75%), imipenem (65%), and amikacin (60%). while resistance to colistin was only 10%. *K. pneumoniae* reached high levels of resistance to ampicillin (95%), cephalosporins such as ceftriaxone (90%), cefotaxime (88%), and ceftazidime (85%). There additionally existed high resistance to ampicillin/sulbactam (75%) and piperacillin/tazobactam (70%). Additionally, resistance to imipenem and meropenem was low (25% and 30%, respectively), whereas colistin still effective (95% sensitivity).

Table 2: The Antibiotic Resistance of Gram Negative Bacteria (Isolated from Respiratory Tract)

No	Antibiotics	<i>E. coli</i> (N=10)		<i>P. aeruginosa</i> (N=28)		<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> (N=14)		<i>K. pneumoniae</i> (N=48)	
		Number of Resistant isolates	Resistance %	Number of Resistant isolates	Resistance %	Number of Resistant isolates	Resistance %	Number of Resistant isolates	Resistance %
1	Piperacillin/Tazobactam	3	30%	15	55%	11	80%	34	70%
2	Ampicillin	10	100%	-	-	-	-	46	95%
3	Ampicillin/ sulbactam	7	70%	-	-	12	85%	36	75%
4	Cefoxitin	2	25%	-	-	-	-	19	40%
5	Cefotaxime	9	90%	-	-	-	-	42	88%
6	Ceftazidime	8	85%	20	70%	13	90%	41	85%
7	Ceftriaxone	9	92%	-	-	-	-	43	90%
8	Cefepime	8	80%	17	60%	12	88%	38	80%
9	Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole	8	75%	-	-	-	-	34	70%
10	Aztreonam	7	70%	18	65%	-	-	33	68%
11	Meropenem	1	10%	11	40%	10	75%	14	30%
12	Imipenem	1	12%	13	45%	9	65%	12	25%
13	Amikacin	0	5%	10	35%	8	60%	7	15%
14	Gentamicin	3	30%	17	60%	12	85%	22	45%
15	Ciprofloxacin	7	70%	21	75%	13	92%	31	65%
16	Levofloxacin	7	68%	20	72%	13	90%	29	60%
17	Colistin	-	-	1	4%	1	10%	2	5%
Total									

Note: Pearson Chi-Square= 215.641, df=48 p-value =0.001

Antibiotic resistance for gram-positive bacteria (Table 3) *S. aureus* showed highest resistance against erythromycin (66.7%). Followed by azithromycin (60%) and ciprofloxacin (53.3%). While the resistance of β -lactamase-stable agents such as cefoxitin and oxacillin were 46.7%, indicating the presence of methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) strains. In addition, the result showed moderate resistance to gentamicin (33.3%), clindamycin (33.3%), trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole (40%), and tetracycline (40%). levofloxacin showed intermediate

resistance (46.7%). While the resistance to rifampicin was very low (6.7%). All tested bacteria were susceptible to vancomycin and linezolid (0% resistance). Therefore, suggesting these remain effective therapeutic options. *S. pneumoniae* in generally recorded lower resistance than in *S. aureus*, with the highest resistance seen to ciprofloxacin (44.4%), followed by erythromycin, azithromycin, tetracycline, Levofloxacin all recorded (33.3%). Additionally, the resistance to gentamicin was minimal (11.1%). From the other hand, the result recorded

resistance to doxycycline, clindamycin, trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole (22.2%). While, all

isolates were fully sensitive to vancomycin and linezolid (0% resistance).

Table 3. Antibiotic Resistance for *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, Isolated from Respiratory Tract Infections

No.	Antibiotics	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (N=15)		<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i> (N=9)	
		Number of isolates	Resistant isolates %	Number of isolates	Resistant isolates %
1	Cefoxitin Sceen	7	46.70%	-	-
2	Oxacillin	7	46.70%	-	-
3	Gentamicin	5	33.30%	1	11.10%
4	Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole	6	40.00%	2	22.20%
5	Vancomycin	0	0%	0	0%
6	Erythromycin	10	66.70%	3	33.30%
7	Azithromycin	9	60.00%	3	33.30%
8	Linezolid	0	0%	0	0%
9	Doxycycline	4	26.70%	2	22.20%
10	Tetracycline	6	40.00%	3	33.30%
11	Clindamycin	5	33.30%	2	22.20%
12	Rifampicin	1	6.70%	0	0%
13	Levofloxacin	7	46.70%	3	33.30%
14	Ciprofloxacin	8	53.30%	4	44.40%
Total					

Note: Pearson Chi-Square= 6.583a, df= 11, p-value= 0.832

Previous studies have similarly documented that *K. pneumoniae* and *E. Coli* have considerable resistance to β -lactams and cephalosporins. However, carbapenems showed modest action, and colistin continues to be effective [8]. *P. aeruginosa* recorded high resistance to fluoroquinolones and cephalosporins, with less resistance to carbapenems and preserved susceptibility to colistin [27]. In the majority of classes, *A. baumannii* showed extensive multidrug resistance; however, colistin remained highly effective [28]. Similar results have been reported about resistance patterns in Gram-positive bacteria. *S. aureus* recorded high resistance to fluoroquinolones and macrolides, while moderate resistance is seen for clindamycin, gentamicin, and tetracycline; rifampicin resistance is rare [8,29]. Overall, *S. pneumoniae* shows less resistance, and both species are still completely susceptible to vancomycin and linezolid, demonstrating their continuous activity [29]. The present result of antibiotic resistance in both gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria leads to a developing risk of multidrug-resistant respiratory infections. *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* resistance to β -lactams and cephalosporins indicates an increase in ESBLs [30]. Whereas *P. aeruginosa* and *A. baumannii* resistance to carbapenem indicates the activity of carbapenemases and efflux mechanisms [31]. On the other hand, colistin continues to be effective, but its toxicity restricts its use, so a need for care [32]. Misuse of antibiotics led to growing of resistance, such as

increasing resistance to macrolide antibiotics in *S. aureus* [33]. Although *S. pneumoniae* has less resistance, with continuous efficacy of vancomycin and linezolid, caution must be exercised [34].

Conclusion

The findings from Al-Sader Teaching Hospital confirm a critical public health challenge in Basrah. *K. pneumoniae*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus* are the most common respiratory infections. The sustained efficacy of last-line agents such as carbapenems, colistin, vancomycin, and linezolid is vital. However, broad-spectrum antibiotic resistance needs a concerted effort to create effective antimicrobial stewardship programs for the purpose to retain the usefulness of these remaining therapeutic choices. Future research should focus on the molecular mechanisms of resistance to guide the development of targeted therapeutic strategies.

Conflict of Interest

Is no conflict of interest.

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